

Achievement of Ancient Myanmar Kings for Irrigation System

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Abstract

When ancient Pyu cities came into existence before King Anawrahta ascended the throne, it was discovered that they had built reservoirs and lakes and made arrangements to obtain regular supply of water for cultivation of crops, by digging canals. Pyus also initiated to employ methods of cultivation by irrigated water along the basin of river Ayeyawady and flooded plain land area. Beikthano, Sriksetra and Kyaukse were congested with the ancient weirs, constructed by ancient Myanmar kings. Although system of cultivation with irrigated water seemed to be an old system, it was very systematic. Irrigation networks, reservoirs and lakes, constructed during the period of Myanmar Kings, were durable and strong.

Keywords : old myanmar irrigation works, reservoirs, canals, weirs

Introduction

Pyus initiated to employ methods of cultivation by irrigated water along the basin of river Ayeyawady and flooded plain land area. At Beikthano city and Sriksetra city of Pyu, irrigation networks were also discovered. The eastern side of Sriksetra was protected by only one wall, much lower and narrower than the others which follow a notably different alignment. Kyaukse District was congested with the ancient weirs, constructed by Myanmar Kings even before 1000A.D. Because of irrigation networks constructed by Myanmar Kings, cultivation could be carried out easily. The method of construction of a dam was to block water flowing along the stream at a place and divert the water flowing from upstream to either side of irrigation networks. It was the basic principle of construction of a dam by the Myanmar of olden days.

Objectives

- To share the talents of ancient myanmar kings.
- To honour the endeavour of ancient myanmar kings concerning with irrigation system.

Myanmar's economy wholly depended on agriculture during Myanmar monarchical period. For that reason method of building weirs and irrigation networks are important for the success of cultivation system in Upper Myanmar where rainfall is scanty. Tributaries canals from great water storage tanks and from creeks to cultivated areas which are the most suitable to cultivate by nature are indefatigable creative efforts of the people. The system of cultivation of crops by irrigated water has existed long before the reign of King Anawrahta of Bagan dynasty.

When ancient Pyu cities came into existence before King Anawrahta ascended the throne, it was discovered that they had built reservoirs and lakes and made arrangements to obtain regular supply of water for cultivation of crops, by digging canals. Pyu also initiated to employ methods of cultivation by irrigated water along the basin of River Ayeyawady and flooded plain land area. Excavation at Taung Thaman Inn region in Amarapura Township reveals clear evidences in relation to cultivation with irrigated water along with stone-age

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evidences. At Beikthano city of Pyu, irrigation networks were also discovered. Aerial survey photographs around Beikthano city show the impression of irrigation, streams, creeks and lakes.

At Sriksetra, the system of cultivation of crops by irrigated water had been carried out as it had been done in Beikthano. Around the area of Sriksetra, big lakes and creeks existed. At Sriksetra the creeks were lined up with bricks. The bricks with a hole in the middle were laid hole to hole. Hence line laid bricks formed as brick pipe lines. Such lines could be observed near Sriksetra. In old Pyu cities weirs and lakes were constructed to get the required water for cultivation.

The eastern side of Sriksetra was protected by only one wall, much lower and narrower than the others which follow a notably different alignment. The aerial photographs indicate the former presence of a large water tank which has been abandoned long ago and whose bed is now occupied by the fields and a swamp. Janice Stargardt suggests that Sriksetra was originally defended on the east by this tank but that sometime in the history of the city, desiccation led to a shrinking of the body of water which it held. It was then decided to fortify the city on this side with a wall and to avoid the down-slope towards the tank bed, it was necessary to construct the East wall on quite a different alignment from the other walls. Sriksetra was the beneficiary of a vast and fully integrated hydraulic system, of which the moats and tanks previously known form only a small part.

Sriksetra possessed 150 linear kilometres of ancient moats and canals and a series of tanks and distributaries channels as well. Sriksetra must be regarded as fully comparable with Angkor in Cambodia with respect to the exceptional density and magnitude of its ancient urban hydraulic development.

The size and material riches of Sriksetra suggest that for many centuries it possessed a vivid economic life in which people and goods moved back and forth from the countryside into the city and vice-versa. Even though just over half of the city's enclave was occupied by fortified fields and irrigation works, these alone would not have sufficed to support its period of greatest prosperity, but were an invaluable resource in time of danger and weakness.

During the reign of ancient Kings, the methods and techniques of construction of weirs were almost the same. The technique of construction of weirs was mostly at its peak in Letwin Koe Khayaing, Kyaukse Khayaing in particular. The method of construction of irrigation networks in Kyaukse District was a particular Myanmar method of constructions. There were no modern instruments to measure the water level; yet, Myanmar made use of the *Khai Chein* (Plumb-bob) which is a hanging plumb-bob on shield shape material. The way to measure nature of ground level was by stretching a rope between two poles tightly and the plumb-bob hung from the rope. A hole was punctured in the plumb-bob. Then a string was threaded through the hole. The string at the lower position of plumb-bob was the surface. By raising and putting down the strings at the lower portion of the plumb-bob, water level could be determined. Thereby Myanmar in olden days knew to what extent declination of the earth to be dug up to enable to drain out the water. In the same way by using the plumb-bob, the surface level of the ground was measured and according to the topography irrigation networks were constructed.

The method of construction of a dam was to block water flowing along the stream at a place and divert the water flowing from up-stream to either side of irrigation networks. It was the basic principle of construction of a dam by the Myanmar of olden days.

The dams' construction work carried out by Myanmar in olden days is as shown in the sketch.

Plan of timber regulator and timber weir.

Source : Janice Stargadt, *The Ancient Pyu of Burma*, p-57.

First, wooden posts measuring six inches in diameter were taken and chopped down to have a prism-like shape. Then toddy palm trunks were erected as props from the bed of the River. Next, the hewn woods in prism forms were placed across the River. After that, above the wood prisms, trunks of toddy palm were placed horizontally and tied together firmly. Four inches thick sharp wooden poles were struck in erect position down to the bed of the River and tied to the pole with stem of the toddy palm which was laid horizontally across the River. To stop the water flowing from up-stream, bamboo mats were placed on the frontal part of the construction works and stones were heaped systematically in front of the bamboo mats.

The dams constructed by local Myanmar techniques required major renovation annually. The timber used for construction of dam and weirs did not last more than three years. Hence, the stones heaped for preventing the flow of water tended to be eroded or moved away by the thrusting power of the current. The dams could be destroyed. Although concrete dams were constructed for durability by the British in later period, it was not required to change the site of the dam which Myanmar had built.

All the methods of construction of weirs were the same. As a first step posts were erected across the River and tied together with stems of toddy palm or wood. The interim spaces were filled with stones. After that a stone slab was placed above the stones. It demonstrates the cleverness in the construction of dams and effectiveness of the construction. But it was required to maintain continuously. Since water could not be sealed tightly, there was a certain amount of water seepage. Since the big stones may last for the time being some small stones may be lost in the current. Thereby the foundations would be exposed. Sometimes big trees tend to float down the River. If it came to collide with the dam, the dam would be destroyed if the foundation be in a state of decay the dam could be destroyed. Thus the people continually had to have a close watch over the dam to maintain it all the time with care.

Kyaukse District was congested with the ancient weirs, constructed by Myanmar Kings even before 1000A.D. *Kyaukse Koe Khayaing* region mainly depended on weirs constructed on Zawgyi and Panlaung Rivers for cultivation. Since, Kyaukse District is situated in rain shadow area, average annual rainfall in the region is not more than 30 inches. But because of irrigation networks constructed by Myanmar Kings, cultivation could be carried out easily. Since the reign of King Anawrahta of Bagan, after construction of seven weirs cultivation had been done with irrigated water.

In conclusion, although system of cultivation with irrigated water seemed to be an old system, it was very systematic. Irrigation networks, reservoirs and lakes, constructed during the period of Myanmar Kings were durable and strong. British government which occupied Myanmar after the Third Anglo-Myanmar War repaired and used the weirs constructed by ancient Myanmar Kings 800 years ago.

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